

A STUDY OF THE INFLUENCE OF MICROSTRUCTURE ON THE MODIFIED
EFFECTIVE MODULUS APPROACH FOR COMPOSITE LAMINATES

E. F. Rybicki
Battelle Columbus Laboratories, Columbus, Ohio 43201

N. J. Pagano
Wright Patterson Air Force Base, Dayton, Ohio 45433

Abstract

Although the effective modulus (EM) representation of composite materials is widely used in the stress analysis and design of structural laminates, there is little understanding for the meaning of EM stress distributions in regions of high stress gradients. The authors present a modified effective modulus (MEM) approach as a means of understanding how EM stress distributions compare with exact solutions in regions of high stress gradients. In a previous study, the authors showed the modified effective modulus approach provided a useful way of comparing EM and exact solutions for a laminate with one fiber size. In this study, the effect of fiber size on the modified effective modulus approach is examined.

Introduction

Currently, the effective modulus representation of composite materials is widely used in the stress analysis and design of structural laminates. In the effective modulus (EM) representation, each layer of the heterogeneous fiber/matrix system is represented by a homogeneous media. The mechanical properties (moduli and Poisson's ratios) of the homogeneous EM media are based on the volume-averaged stresses and strains in a representative volume element of the heterogeneous media. The EM approach has received more attention than the heterogeneous representation, because in all but the simplest applications the latter is not economically feasible. However, the EM representation is valid only when the stress fields of the EM model are uniform [1-4]. In most design applications, the stress fields do not remain uniform throughout the EM model. Examples are stress distributions in the vicinity of edges, holes, and joints. Because these geometric features are common to structural components, it is important to have an understanding of the laminate behavior in these areas. Thus, the EM stress analysis of laminates contains the dilemma that although it is widely used in the stress analysis of laminates, there is little understanding of the significance of EM solutions in regions of high stress gradients.

One means of examining the meaning of the EM approach in the region of high stress gradients is to compare the stress distributions of an EM representation with those of a heterogeneous or micromechanics (MM) model. Pagano and Rybicki [5] carried out such a study and hypothesized an approach to relate the EM and MM (exact) stress fields. This approach is referred to here as the modified effective modulus (MEM) approach. In this approach, the EM stress fields are calculated in the usual way. These stress fields are then reinterpreted by calculating the average stresses over the dimensions of the representative volume elements. For example, in the case of square fiber spacing, the representative volume element is the basic square of matrix material containing a single fiber. The length of the side of this square is equal to the fiber spacing and is the length over which the stresses from the EM solution are averaged. Central to the MEM approach is the assumption that the average stress, calculated from the EM solution, is approximately equal to the average stress of the corresponding representative volume element in the MM solution.

Numerical evidence in support of the MEM approach was presented in Reference [5]. Although the EM representation failed to predict the correct sign of the maximum stress, there was a very good correlation between the average stresses from the two approaches. This result indicates that the MEM approach may provide a basis for interpreting the EM solutions in regions

of high stress gradients.

It is recognized that the laminate in Reference [5] had a particular fiber size and fiber volume. Examining different fiber sizes is important because fiber diameters range from "large" in boron/epoxy laminates to "small" in graphite/epoxy and fiberglass laminates. In this work, additional numerical support is given for the MEM approach as the influence of microstructure on the MEM approach is examined by varying fiber sizes without changing the percent fiber volume so that the EM solutions are unchanged.

Laminate Models and Stress Analysis

To examine the effect of fiber size, the fiber diameters were varied with respect to the laminate thickness. The laminates considered here have four layers. The two outside layers are reinforced with fibers oriented at 0 degrees. The center two layers are unreinforced. Two basic types of laminate representations were considered for the stress analysis. One type was the EM representation where the body is represented as a laminate consisting of four homogeneous layers. The second type involved the MM models, which recognized the individual fibers. For the case of linear elastic material behavior and small deformations and strains, this model can be considered to be exact. Boron/Epoxy properties with one, two, three, and forty rows of fibers through a lamina thickness were considered. Figure 1 shows a symmetric quadrant of each laminate and the corresponding MM representations for the stress analysis. In these models, a portion of the heterogeneous structure has been replaced by EM properties in accordance with the observation [5] that the influence of a given fiber dies out within a length of one fiber spacing.

The loading condition for each case was a uniform extension in the fiber direction causing a unit tensile strain, ϵ_x . We are particularly concerned with the high values of σ_z near a free edge of the laminate. The material properties of the fiber, matrix, and those for the EM model are given in Table I. The fiber volume content for all reinforced lamina was 0.282.

The stress distributions for these models were obtained with a finite-element analysis described in Reference [6]. Up to 1006 nodes and 970 elements were used in the finite-element models.

Table I. Material Properties

Fiber	Matrix
$E_f = 60 \times 10^6$ psi	$E_m = 0.5 \times 10^6$ psi
$V_f = 0.2$	$V_m = 0.34$
<u>Effective Modulus</u>	
$E_x = 17.8 \times 10^6$ psi	$E_y = 10^6$ psi
$V_{xy} = 0.3$	$G_{yx} = 0.274 \times 10^6$ psi
$V_{yz} = 0.44$	

Discussion of Results

Figure 2 shows the σ_z stress distributions at the interface between the reinforced and the unreinforced laminae. A comparison of results is shown for the EM model* and the models containing two and three rows of fibers. It is seen that the maximum compression and tension stresses occur for the model with three rows of fibers. Thus, the stress gradients are higher for the three rows of fibers than for two rows. Still higher gradients were found for the model with 40 rows of fibers. Figure 3 shows the σ_z stress distributions at the midplane of the laminate for the various models. This figure shows that the σ_z stress distribution at the laminate center is essentially unchanged by the fiber size.

The presence of the free edge creates high stress gradients within each lamina. To illustrate this, Figure 4 shows three stress distributions for the interlaminar stress, σ_z , near the free edge. These curves show the peak compressive value of σ_z occurs at the center of the laminate. The maximum tensile stress does not occur at the interface between the two laminae but at a point within the top lamina. The stress distributions shown in Figure 4 have similar shapes. The magnitude of these stresses is decreasing rapidly in the direction away from the free edge. This reflects the gradient in σ_z shown in Figure 3.

The most significant result from this study is the comparison of the average interlaminar stress, σ_z , from the micro-mechanics models and those calculated by the modified effective

*We have utilized a more refined grid system for the EM model here, hence the EM result shown in Figure 2 differs slightly from that given in [5]. This difference is not sufficient to change the numerical results presented in [5].

modulus approach. Figure 5 shows close agreement between the average stresses from the EM approach and those from the MM model for the fiber nearest the free edge. This figure shows that the average compressive stress for two rows of fibers is larger than that for the single row of fibers. The average stress for three rows is very close to the result for two rows. However, when the number of fiber rows is increased to forty, the average stress for the end fiber changes sign to a tensile value as does the average stress from the modified effective modulus approach.

The models for one, two and three rows of fibers are straight forward, but some discussion of the model for forty rows is in order. Forty rows of fibers per lamina were selected to determine if the average interlaminar stress for an edge fiber was tensile as indicated by the MEM approach. It can be seen from Figure 5 that this was found to be true. A finite element representation of all forty rows of fibers was not possible because of size limitations imposed by the computer program. Thus, a smaller number of fibers was selected to be modeled individually and surrounded by material with effective modulus properties. With the models for two and three rows of fibers, a boundary layer equal to the fiber spacing was observed near the interface of the effective modulus material and the heterogeneous fiber/matrix material. Based on this observation, a model with nine fibers in a three by three square was selected. It was reasoned that the edge fiber at the interface between the laminae would then be out of the observed boundary layer. As a further check, a four fiber representation in the form of a two by two square, surrounded by material with effective modulus properties, was also modeled. A comparison of the average values for the σ_z stresses obtained from the three by three and two by two fiber squares showed good agreement. This comparison was done to examine the validity of the model for the case of forty rows of fibers. A model containing a single fiber surrounded by material with effective modulus properties was also considered. As one might expect, the resulting average stress was largely influenced by the observed boundary effect due to the proximity of the effective modulus material. Thus a single fiber is inadequate for modeling the lamina with forty rows of fibers.

Summary and Conclusions

Currently, there is little understanding for the meaning of EM stress distributions in regions of high stress gradients. In this study, the modified effective modulus approach is examined as a means of understanding how EM solutions compare with the exact MM solutions in regions of high stress gradients. A previous study, Reference [5], showed the modified effective modulus approach provided a useful way of comparing EM and MM

solutions for a laminate with one fiber size. In this study, the effect of fiber size on the modified effective modulus approach is examined.

The modified effective modulus approach reinterprets the results of the effective modulus solutions in terms of average stresses over a length equal to the length of a side of the representative volume element. Laminates with the same fiber content but different fiber diameters were considered. Regions with high stress gradients were examined near the laminate free edge. Solutions were obtained for laminates with one, two, three, and forty rows of fibers through a lamina thickness. For the laminates considered here, the study showed that the distribution of the transverse stress, σ_z at the laminate midplane was not changed by the fiber diameter and also that the stress gradients in the reinforced laminae tended to increase as the fiber diameters decreased. The most significant finding was the close correlation between the average stress values obtained from the modified effective modulus approach and the average stresses from the micromechanics models. Thus, for the laminates considered here, the results provide additional numerical support for the validity of the MEM approach. Hence, the average stress as defined in the modified effective modulus approach, appears to be a useful quantity for interpreting the effective modulus solutions in regions of high stress gradients.

Acknowledgements

The authors wish to acknowledge P. A. Hayes for her assistance in conducting the finite element stress analyses.

References

1. Hashin, Z., "Theory of Mechanical Behavior of Heterogeneous Media", Applied Mechanics Reviews, Vol. 17, 1964, pp 1.
2. Jaunzemis, W., "An Application of Strain-Gradient Theory to Nonhomogeneous Materials", Fiber Science and Technology, Vol. 1, 1968, pp 11.
3. Tabaddor, F., "A Note on Effective Moduli of Composite Materials", J. Appl. Mech., Vol. 39, 1972, pp 598.
4. Pagano, N. J., "The Role of Effective Moduli in the Elastic Analysis of Composite Laminates", in Mechanics of Composite Materials, G. P. Sendeckyj, ed., Academic Press, N.Y., to be published.

5. Pagano, N. J. and Rybicki, E. F., "On the Significance of Effective Modulus Solutions for Fibrous Composites", J. Composite Materials, Vol. 8, 1974, pp 214.
6. Wilson, E. L., "Structural Analysis of Axisymmetric Solids", AIAA J., Vol. 3, 1965, pp 2269.

FIGURE 1. LAMINATES AND THE MODELS FOR STRESS ANALYSIS. (One Quarter of Each Laminate Shown.)

FIGURE 2. COMPARISON OF INTERLAMINAR STRESS DISTRIBUTIONS AT $Z = h$ FOR THE EM MODEL AND THE MODELS FOR TWO AND THREE ROWS OF FIBERS (Loading is $\epsilon_x = 1.0$)

FIGURE 3. COMPARISON OF THE INTERLAMINAR STRESS DISTRIBUTIONS AT THE LAMINATE CENTER FOR DIFFERENT FIBER SIZES

FIGURE 4. INTERLAMINAR STRESS DISTRIBUTIONS NEAR FREE EDGE (Loading $\epsilon_x = 1.0$)

FIGURE 5. COMPARISON OF AVERAGE STRESS VALUES FROM THE EXACT FIBER/MATRIX MODEL AND THE MODIFIED EFFECTIVE MODULUS APPROACH